

Approximation-Based Nussbaum-Gain Adaptive Neural Fault-Tolerant Prescribed-Performance Control for Saturated MIMO Nonlinear Systems: A Non-Backstepping Approach

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Abstract

In this paper, an active fault-tolerant (AFT) adaptive tracking control problem, with guaranteed a priori prescribed performance, is developed for a class of multi-input multi-output (MIMO) pure-feedback nonlinear systems subject, simultaneously, to input saturation, output constraints, and unknown actuator faults. In the suggested fault-tolerant adaptive control method, neural networks (NNs) are used to understand unknown nonlinear behaviors, reduce the impact of input saturation, and manage three additive and one multiplicative actuator faults without needing a separate fault unit. The proposed AFT controller design avoids the difficulty due to the recursive design procedure in controlling cascading MIMO nonlinear systems by reformulating the original constrained MIMO control problem into an unconstrained MIMO feedback control problem in controllable form with a dynamic control input to avoid the algebraic loop problem usually encountered in AFT control. To estimate unknown states of the newly derived canonical system, an adaptive NNs observer is adopted, and the knowledge of control directions is circumvented by using the Nussbaum-type functions. Furthermore, the proposed AFT controller is designed to guarantee a priori prescribed performance with only a few adaptive parameters by using the common Lyapunov stability method. Simulations on a model and a quadrotor UAV validate the proposed control scheme.

Keywords: NNs adaptive control, MIMO Nonlinear pure-feedback Systems, Nussbaum-type function, Actuator faults, Prescribed performance, Input saturation.

1. Introduction

Due to the challenges of control theory and practical applications, many significant results in the field of adaptive control of nonlinear systems have been obtained during the past decades. Therefore, various attempts have been made to develop approximation-based adaptive back-stepping control schemes for strict-feedback uncertain MIMO nonlinear systems [1, 2]. However, these findings were expanded to address the tougher challenge of controlling uncertain non-affine pure-feedback MIMO nonlinear systems, using effective control methods like those in [3, 4]. Despite these efforts on MIMO systems, only a few of the existing results consider the problem of the constraints on inputs and outputs along with unknown control directions. In practice, output constraints, including the inherent physical and safety limitations of a real system, pose a challenging issue that can lead to degradation of system performance and even instability. Therefore, the rigorous handling of constraints in control design and analysis is an important topic in the control community. To address this problem, numerous works in the literature ensure that the constraints are satisfied. In [5], a strong adaptive controller is created for marine vessel systems that uses the barrier Lyapunov function (BLF) to make sure the speed limits are not broken. In [6, 7], the integral barrier Lyapunov function (IBLF) was created to handle limits

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on the states. On the other hand, methods that use transformations, which were first introduced in prescribed performance control (PPC) in [8, 9], have been applied to manage constraints in MIMO nonlinear systems. In [10], a specific time-based performance function (ATPPF) has been suggested for controlling uncertain QUAVs with adaptive dynamic surface tracking.

Another challenge in designing control strategies for cascade MIMO nonlinear systems is the potential overloading of actuators, which leads to issues similar to those caused by output constraints. This problem has been addressed in the literature using various techniques. For instance, in [11]–[13], a hyperbolic tangent function was employed to approximate the saturation nonlinearity, and the bounded approximation error was lumped into the external disturbance term. A robust control component was then designed to compensate for this effect. In [14], an auxiliary system was introduced to counteract the impact of input saturation. Meanwhile, [15] employed the mean-value theorem as a smooth approximation to efficiently address actuator input saturation.

Furthermore, in practice, various components such as sensors and actuators may undergo failures during operation and can cause system instability. In recent years, many adaptive fuzzy or NN fault-tolerant control (FTC) design methods have been proposed to solve the problem of sensor and actuator faults to maintain acceptable system performance. In [16]–[19], models for faults were introduced to achieve the FTC problem for MIMO systems by using a back-stepping approach. The actuator faults were considered in [16, 17]; however, simultaneous sensor and actuator faults were considered in [18, 19].

In many existing MIMO adaptive control methods, the backstepping approach has been widely adopted; however, it often suffers from excessive complexity due to the repeated derivation of virtual control signals. To mitigate this issue, dynamic surface control (DSC) was introduced, employing filtered virtual control laws [20, 21]. Despite its advantages, DSC still presents several limitations that hinder its broader applicability. An alternative solution, the command-filtered DSC method, has been proposed in [22, 23] to further alleviate the complexity. Nevertheless, challenges remain, particularly the recursive design process inherent in backstepping, which results in cumbersome control structures for high-order systems and requires the online adaptation of a large number of parameters. In [24]–[26], neural/fuzzy adaptive control methods restricted to SISO nonlinear systems, in pure-feedback or strict-feedback forms, were achieved without using back-stepping procedures, while a large number of practical systems possess multivariable characteristics. Analyzing nonlinear higher-order cascade MIMO systems, such as unmanned aerial vehicles, is more complicated due to state and input interconnections within dynamics, making the extension of designs from SISO systems to cascade MIMO systems far from trivial.

We believe that figuring out how to control input-saturated pure feedback MIMO nonlinear systems that have actuator faults and output limits is still a significant and difficult problem in both theory and real-life situations. In this paper, the objective is to design an adaptive NNs control, with guaranteed a priori prescribed performance, for a class of pure-feedback MIMO nonlinear systems in the simultaneous presence of input saturation, output constraints, actuator faults, and unknown control directions without using back-stepping techniques. First, we introduce models for all types of actuator faults such as bias, drift, loss of accuracy, and loss of effectiveness along with the approximation of the saturation nonlinearity into the MIMO pure-feedback dynamic system with constrained outputs. The model is changed into a MIMO controllable affine form and then adjusted into an unconstrained MIMO normal form with a dynamic control input to prevent the algebraic loop problem that often comes up in controller design in [27, 28]. Then, an auxiliary system is introduced to decrease the effect of the input saturation along with a Nussbaum-type function to deal with the problem of unknown control directions. The adaptive NNs tracking controllers are designed with only a few adaptive parameters by using the common Lyapunov stability theorem. Finally, we present simulation results that demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed control scheme. This paper summarizes its main contributions in comparison to the literature.

1. In [1]–[7], [14],[16],[18], researchers faced a common issue where the complexity increased a lot because of the derivatives from several virtual control laws in the cascade type of MIMO nonlinear systems. However, the proposed scheme adopts a non-back-stepping approach, which completely avoids the problem.

2. Although the problem of the explosion of complexity of MIMO systems was solved in [9, 12, 21] by using DSC and filtered command approaches, multiple virtual control laws are always needed such that the number of adaptive parameters is still high and depends on the order of the system due to the recursive nature of the adopted approaches. Conversely, regardless of the system's order, the proposed controller requires only three adaptive parameters, negating the need for virtual controllers.
3. In [24]–[26], the problem of the explosion of complexity and the reduction of the number of adaptive parameters was solved for the case of SISO systems. This work extends the results to address MIMO cascade nonlinear systems. It is important to mention that studying nonlinear higher-order cascade MIMO systems is more difficult because of the connections between states and inputs in the dynamics, making it challenging to apply the design from SISO to MIMO systems. Unlike the SISO cases, we adopt a dynamic input to circumvent the algebraic loop problem.
4. The suggested control method for pure-feedback MIMO nonlinear systems not only solves problems but also tackles several real-world challenges at the same time, such as input saturation, output limits, and actuator failures. However, only individual realistic problems were considered in the literature on MIMO control systems with cascade configurations, along with the previously cited shortcomings in [1]–[7],[9, 12],[16]–[18], [24]–[26].

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the problem formulation is presented. Section 3 first presents a system transformation technique, followed by the proposal of a detailed controller design methodology that ensures the satisfaction of output constraints. Simulation results are presented to show the effectiveness of the proposed controller in Section 4. Section 5 contains the conclusion.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND PRELIMINARIES

2.1. System Descriptions

Consider the following class of MIMO pure-feedback nonlinear systems:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{x}_{i1} &= f_{i1}(x_{i1}, x_{i2}) \\
\dot{x}_{i2} &= f_{i2}(\bar{x}_{i2}, x_{i3}) \\
&\dots\dots\dots \\
\dot{x}_{i,n_i-1} &= f_{i,n_i-1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i}) \\
\dot{x}_{i,n_i} &= f_{i,n_i}(X, u_i^f) \\
y_i &= x_{i1}
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $\bar{x}_{ij} = [x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{ij}]^T \in \mathfrak{R}^j, (i = 1, \dots, N), j = 1, \dots, n_i; x_i = [x_{i1}, \dots, x_{i,n_i}]^T \in \mathfrak{R}^{n_i}, X = [x_1, \dots, x_N]$ and $y_i = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N]^T \in \mathfrak{R}$ are the state and output vectors, respectively. $f_{ij}(\cdot), (i = 1, \dots, N; j = 1, \dots, n_i)$ are unknown but smooth nonlinear functions, u_i^f is the control input with actuator faults and saturations, which can be described as:

$$u_i^f = \rho_i(t)u_i(v_i) + d_{i,v}(t) \tag{2}$$

where $\rho_i(t)$ and $d_{i,v}(t)$ are the unknown actuator effectiveness and the additive actuation faults, respectively. $u_i(v_i) \in \mathfrak{R}^m$ denotes the control input subject to saturations with inputs $v_i(t)$ and outputs $u(v) = [u_1(v_1), \dots, u_M(v_M)]$ which can be expressed as:

$$u_i(v_i) = \text{sat}(v_i) = \begin{cases} -u_{iM} & \text{if } |v_i(t)| < u_{iM} \\ v_i & \text{if } -u_{iM} \leq |v_i(t)| \leq u_{iM} \\ u_{iM} & \text{if } |v_i(t)| > u_{iM} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

where u_{iM} are the bounds of $u_i(v_i), i = 1, \dots, M$. It should be noted that a sharp corner exists when $|v_i(t)| = u_{iM}$ which makes the control signal abruptly change. To avoid this, the saturation is approximated by a hyperbolic tangent function, the $\text{sat}(v_i)$ in (3) can be expressed as

$$\text{sat}(v_i(t)) = h(v_i) + \Upsilon(v_i) \quad (4)$$

$$h(v_i) = u_{iM} \times \tanh\left(\frac{v_i}{u_{iM}}\right) = u_{iM} \frac{e^{\left(\frac{v_i}{u_{iM}}\right)} - e^{-\left(\frac{v_i}{u_{iM}}\right)}}{e^{\left(\frac{v_i}{u_{iM}}\right)} + e^{-\left(\frac{v_i}{u_{iM}}\right)}} \quad (5)$$

where $\Upsilon(v_i) = \text{sat}(v_i(t)) - h(v_i)$ is a bounded function $i = 1, \dots, m$, and the bound of $\Upsilon(v_i)$ satisfies:

$$|\Upsilon(v_i)| = |\text{sat}(v_i(t)) - h(v_i)| \leq u_{iM}(1 - \tanh(1)) \quad (6)$$

The saturation $h_i(v_i)$ is defined as follows:

$$\Delta u_i = u_i(v_i) - v_i = h(v_i) + \Upsilon(v_i) - v_i \quad (7)$$

where $h(v_i) = \Delta u_i + v_i - \Upsilon(v_i)$.

Moreover, there often exist actuator faults in the practical systems. By combining (2) with (7), the failures that may occur on this actuator can be modeled as:

$$\begin{aligned} u_i^f &= \rho_i(t)(h(v_i) + \Upsilon(v_i)) + d_{i,v}(t) \\ &= \rho_i(t)v_i + \rho_i(t)\Delta u_i + d_{i,v}(t), \forall t \leq T_{fi} \\ &= v_i + \Delta u_i + f_{ai} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $f_{ai} = (\rho_i(t) - 1)(v_i + \Delta u_i) + d_{i,v}(t)$ is actuator fault; T_{fi} is the time instant of failure for the i^{th} actuator.

Assumption 1. ([29]) *The actuator effectiveness parameters $\rho_i(t)$ and additive faults $d_{i,v}(t)$ are bounded, that is, $\rho_i(t) \in [\bar{\rho}_i, 1]$ and $d_{i,v}(t) \in [-\bar{d}_{i,v}, \bar{d}_{i,v}]$ where $\bar{\rho}_i > 0$ and $\bar{d}_{i,v} > 0$ are unknown constants.*

In this paper, we are dealing with three additive (drift, loss of accuracy, and bias) and one multiplicative (loss of effectiveness) actuator faults. A more detailed explanation about the studied faults is presented in Table 1 as in [30].

Table 1: Time-varying Actuator Faults

Actuator	Fault Kind	Fault Expression	Fault Type
$u_i^f(t)$	$u_i(t) + d_{i,v}(t)$	$\rho_i = 1, \dot{d}_{i,v}(t) = 0, d_{i,v}(T_{fi}) \neq 0, \forall t \leq T_{fi}$	Bias (Lock in Place)
	$u_i(t) + d_{i,v}(t)$	$\rho_i = 1, \dot{d}_{i,v}(t) = \lambda_i t, 0 < \lambda_i \ll 1, \forall t \leq T_{fi}$	Drift
	$u_i(t) + d_{i,v}(t)$	$\rho_i = 1, d_{i,v}(t) \leq \bar{d}_{i,v}, \dot{d}_{i,v}(t) \rightarrow 0, \forall t \leq T_{fi}$	Loss of Accuracy
	$\rho_i(t) \cdot u_i(t)$	$d_{i,v}(t) = 0, 0 < \bar{\rho}_i \leq \rho_i(t) \leq 1, \forall t \leq T_{fi}$	Loss of Effectiveness

Assumption 2. *The reference signals $y_{id}(t), (i = 1, \dots, N)$ together with its derivatives up to order $(n_i + 1)^{\text{th}}$ are smooth and bounded.*

Lemma 1. ([31]) *For $\forall \zeta q \in \Re$ the following inequality holds*

$$0 \leq |q| - q \tanh\left(\frac{q}{\zeta}\right) \leq \kappa \zeta \quad (9)$$

where $\kappa = 0.2785$

The control objective is to design an adaptive NNs controller for a class of pure-feedback MIMO non-linear systems in the presence of actuator faults, input saturation, output constraints, and unknown directions such that

P1. The system output $y_i(t)$ follows the desired output signals $y_{id}(t)$, while all the signals of the closed-loop system are bounded.

P2. The tracking errors $e_i(t) = y_i(t) - y_{id}(t)$ achieve both prescribed transient and steady-state performance.

2.2. Nussbaum function

A function $N(\zeta)$ can be viewed as a Nussbaum-type function if it satisfies [32]:

$$\begin{cases} \lim_{s \rightarrow +\infty} \sup \frac{1}{s} \int_0^s N(\zeta) d\zeta = +\infty \\ \lim_{s \rightarrow +\infty} \inf \frac{1}{s} \int_0^s N(\zeta) d\zeta = -\infty \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Here, the even function $N(\zeta) = \zeta^2 \cos(\zeta)$ satisfying the above equalities will be employed in this paper to handle the control problem of unknown signs.

Lemma 2. ([33]) *Let $V(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ are smooth functions on the interval $[0, t_f)$, with $V(t) \geq 0, \forall t \in [0, t_f)$ and $N(\zeta)$ is an even smooth Nussbaum-type function. If the following inequality holds:*

$$V(t) \leq c_0 + e^{c_1 t} \int_0^t (g(\tau) N(\zeta(\tau)) + 1) \dot{\zeta}(\tau) e^{c_1 \tau} d\tau \quad (11)$$

where c_0 and c_1 are positive constants, and $g(\cdot)$ is a time-varying parameter that takes values in the unknown closed intervals $I = [\underline{l}, \bar{l}]$ with $0 \notin I$, then $V(t)$, $\zeta(t)$, and $\int_0^t g(\tau) N(\zeta) \dot{\zeta} d\tau$ are bounded on $[0, t_f)$.

2.3. Neural networks

Neural networks are universal approximators where a continuous function $f(Z) : \mathfrak{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ can be approached as follows:

$$\hat{f}(Z/\hat{W}) = \hat{W}^T S(Z) \quad (12)$$

where $Z \in \Omega_Z \subset \mathfrak{R}^m$ is the input to NNs, $\hat{W} \in \mathfrak{R}^N$ is the NNs weight vector, and N is the number of NNs nodes, $S(Z) = [s_1(Z), \dots, s_N(Z)]^T$ is chosen to be hyperbolic tangent function as a vector of activation function given by:

$$s_i(Z) = (1 - e^{-Z}) / (1 + e^{-Z}), \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (13)$$

Thanks to the approximation property of NNs [34, 35], for any continuous function, over a compact set Ω_z , there exists N nodes with an optimal weight vector $\hat{W} \in \mathfrak{R}^N$ such that:

$$W_i = \operatorname{argmin}_W \left\{ \sup_{z \in \Omega_z} |\hat{f}(Z/W) - f(Z)| \right\} \quad (14)$$

In other terms, if N is sufficiently large, then $W^T S(Z)$ can approximate $f(Z)$ to any degree of accuracy. In general, the approximation error $\sup_{z \in \Omega_z} |\hat{f}(Z/W) - f(Z)|$ decreases as N increases. More precisely, we may substitute, with no loss of generality, the uncertain function by a NNs plus a modeling error term $\forall Z \in \Omega_z$, as follows:

$$f(Z) = W^T S(Z) + \varepsilon(Z) \quad (15)$$

where W is the optimal weights vector which minimizes the approximation error $\varepsilon(Z)$. Using the NNs universal approximation property [36], $\varepsilon(Z)$ is bounded by an unknown constant $\bar{\varepsilon} > 0$ such that:

$$|\varepsilon(Z)| \leq \bar{\varepsilon} \quad (16)$$

3. Controller methodology

3.1. System transformation

To circumvent the design difficulties introduced by cascading for a pure-feedback MIMO system with input and output constraints. Unlike the system transformation method in [26] for SISO cases, are considered here for MIMO cases by adopting some new state variables and coordinate transforms.

$\{z_{i1}, \dots, z_{i, n_i+1}\}$ as follows:

Step i,1 ($i=1, \dots, N$): Define new state $z_{i1} = y_i = x_{i1} \triangleq \varphi_{i1}(x_{i1})$, and the time derivative of z_{i1} is expressed in the following step.

Step i,2: Let $z_{i2} = \dot{z}_{i1} = f_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2}) \triangleq \varphi_{i2}(\bar{x}_{i2})$, and the time derivative of z_{i2} can be expressed as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}_{i2} &= \frac{\partial f_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2})}{\partial x_{i1}} \dot{x}_{i1} + \frac{\partial f_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2})}{\partial x_{i2}} \dot{x}_{i2} \\ &= \frac{\partial f_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2})}{\partial x_{i1}} f_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2}) + \frac{\partial f_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2})}{\partial x_{i2}} f_{i2}(\bar{x}_{i3}) \\ &\triangleq \varphi_{i3}(\bar{x}_{i3}) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The following fact holds

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_{i3}(\bar{x}_{i3})}{\partial x_{i3}} = \frac{\partial f_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2})}{\partial x_{i2}} \frac{\partial f_{i2}(\bar{x}_{i3})}{\partial x_{i3}} = g_{i1}(\bar{x}_{i2}) g_{i2}(\bar{x}_{i3}) \quad (18)$$

Step i,j ($i = 1, \dots, N$) ($j = 3, \dots, n_{i-1}$): By a similar way, let $z_{ij} = \dot{z}_{i,j-1} \triangleq \varphi_{ij}(\bar{x}_{ij})$, for the i^{th} subsystem, we extend this coordinate transformation to $j = 3, \dots, n_{i-1}$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}_{ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,j}(\bar{x}_{i,j})}{\partial x_{ik}} \dot{x}_{i,k} + \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,j}(\bar{x}_{i,j})}{\partial x_{ij}} \dot{x}_{ij} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,j}(\bar{x}_{i,j})}{\partial x_{ik}} f_{ik}(\bar{x}_{i,k+1}) \\ &\quad + \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,j}(\bar{x}_{i,j})}{\partial x_{ij}} f_{ij}(\bar{x}_{i,j+1}) \\ &= \varphi_{i,j+1}(\bar{x}_{i,j+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Furthermore, the following fact holds:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,j+1}(\bar{x}_{i,j+1})}{\partial x_{i,j+1}} &= \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,j}(\bar{x}_{i,j})}{\partial x_{ij}} \cdot \frac{\partial f_{ij}(\bar{x}_{i,j+1})}{\partial x_{i,j+1}} \\ &= \prod_{k=1}^j g_{k,j}(\bar{x}_{i,k+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Step i, n_i: Let $z_{in_i} = \dot{z}_{i, n_i} \triangleq \varphi_{in_i}(\bar{x}_{in_i})$, its time derivative is:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}_{in_i} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i, n_i}(\bar{x}_{i, n_i})}{\partial x_{ik}} \dot{x}_{i,k} + \frac{\partial \varphi_{i, n_i}(\bar{x}_{i, n_i})}{\partial x_{in_i}} \dot{x}_{in_i} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i, n_i}(\bar{x}_{i, n_i})}{\partial x_{ik}} f_{ik}(\bar{x}_{i,k+1}) \\ &\quad + \frac{\partial \varphi_{i, n_i}(\bar{x}_{i, n_i})}{\partial x_{in_i}} \times \left(f_{i, n_i}(X, u_i^f) \right) \\ &= \varphi_{in_i+1}(\bar{x}_{in_i+1}, u_i^f) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Step $i, n_i + 1$: This is the final step, $z_{in_i+1} = \dot{z}_{i,n_i} \triangleq \varphi_{in_i+1}(\bar{x}_{in_i+1})$, its time derivative is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{z}_{in_i+1} &= \sum_{k=1}^{n_i} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i+1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i+1}, u_i^f)}{\partial x_{ik}} \dot{x}_{i,k} \\
&+ \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i+1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i+1}, u_i^f)}{\partial u_i^f} \dot{u}_i^f \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i+1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i+1}, u_i^f)}{\partial x_{ik}} \dot{x}_{i,k} \\
&+ \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i}, u_i^f)}{\partial u_i^f} \dot{u}_i^f \\
&+ \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i+1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i+1}, u_i^f)}{\partial x_{in_i}} f_{i,n_i}(X, u_i^f)
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Therefore, the original pure-feedback MIMO nonlinear system (88) is transformed into the following normal form that includes a dynamic control input:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{z}_{i,j_i} &= z_{i,j_i+1}, \quad j = 1, \dots, n_i + 1; i = 1, \dots, N \\
\dot{z}_{i,n_i+1} &= F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f(t)) \dot{u}_i^f
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

where $F_i(X, u_i^f) = \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i+1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i+1}, u_i^f)}{\partial x_{ik}} f_{ik}(\bar{x}_{i,k+1}) + \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i+1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i+1}, u_i^f)}{\partial x_{in_i}} f_{i,n_i}(X, u_i^f)$;
 $G_i(X, u_i^f) = \frac{\partial \varphi_{i,n_i+1}(\bar{x}_{i,n_i+1}, u_i^f)}{\partial x_{in_i}}$

Assumption 3. *The sign of the control gain $G_i(\cdot)$ is unknown, and for controllability purpose there exist unknown positive constants \bar{g}_i such as $\|G_i(\cdot)\| \leq \bar{g}_i \leq 0$.*

Equivalently, (23) can be rewritten in compact form as

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{z}_i &= A_i z_i + B_i [F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f(t)) \dot{u}_i^f] \\
y_i &= C_i^T z_i
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where $z_i = [z_{i1}, z_{i2}, \dots, z_{i,n_i+1}]^T$, $A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I^{(n_i)} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, $B = [0 \ \dots \ 1]^T$ and $C = [1 \ \dots \ 0]^T$, with constant matrixes $A_i \in \mathfrak{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$, $B_i, C_i \in \mathfrak{R}^{(n) \times 1}$.

Note that the pair (A_i, B_i) is controllable and the pair (C_i^T, A_i) is observable. Since the system states are unmeasurable, we use the proposed NNs system (12) to design an adaptive NN observer.

3.2. Observer design

To estimate the states of system (24), an adaptive NNs based observer is designed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{\hat{z}}_i &= (A_i - B_i \underline{k}_{ic}^T) \hat{z}_i + P_i^{-1} C_i^T \hat{W}_{i0}^T S_{i0} (Z_{i0}) + \underline{k}_{i0} \tilde{z}_{i1} \\
\hat{y}_i &= C_i^T \hat{z}_i
\end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

with \hat{z}_i the estimate of the state vector z_i and the estimation error is defined by $\tilde{z}_i = \hat{z}_i - z_i = [\tilde{z}_i, \dot{\tilde{z}}_i, \dots, \tilde{z}_i^{(n_i+1)}]^T$ with $\tilde{z}_{i1} = \hat{z}_{i1} - z_{i1}$. Let $\underline{k}_{ic} = [k_{ic}^1, k_{ic}^2, \dots, k_{ic}^{n_i+1}]^T$ be the feedback gain vector,

and $\underline{k}_{i0} = [k_{i0}^1, k_{i0}^2, \dots, k_{i0}^{n_i+1}]^T$ is the observer gain vector, and they will be chosen such that the characteristic polynomials of $(A_i - B_i \underline{k}_{i0}^T)$ and $(A_i - \underline{k}_{i0} C_i^T)$ are Hurwitz. Thus, for any given positive definite symmetric matrix $Q_i = Q_i^T > 0$, then $Q_i + \bar{A}_{i0} \bar{A}_{i0}^T = (Q_i + \bar{A}_{i0} \bar{A}_{i0}^T)^T > 0$, there exists a unique positive definite symmetric solution P to the following Lyapunov algebraic equation:

$$\bar{A}_{i0}^T P_i + P_i \bar{A}_{i0} = - (Q_i + \bar{A}_{i0} \bar{A}_{i0}^T) \quad (26)$$

and $\bar{A}_{i0} = (A_i - \underline{k}_{i0} C_i^T)$ is stable and $B_{i0} = [1, b_{i1}, \dots, b_{i n_i + 1}]^T$, with

$$B_{i0} = P_i^{-1} C_i^T \quad (27)$$

According to (27), it is apparent that

$$\tilde{z}_i^T P_i B_{i0} = \tilde{z}_i^T C_i = \tilde{z}_{i1} \quad (28)$$

3.3. Error estimation transformation

decreasing smooth function $\mu_i(t) : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ with $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_i(t) = \mu_{i\infty} > 0, \mu_{i0} = \mu_i(0) > \mu_{i\infty}$, will be used as the prescribed performance function (PPF), as defined in [8]. Let consider that the tracking error $e_{i1}(t) = y_i(t) - y_{id}(t)$ with $e_i(t) = [z_{i1} - y_{id}, \dots, z_{i n_i} - y_{id}^{(n_i-1)}]^T = [e_{i1}, \dot{e}_{i1}, \dots, e_{i1}^{(n_i-1)}]^T$, must satisfy the following predefined performance inequality:

$$-\underline{\delta}_i \mu_i(t) < e_{i1}(t) < \bar{\delta}_i \mu_i(t), \forall t > 0 \quad (29)$$

where $\underline{\delta}_i$ and $\bar{\delta}_i > 0$ are constants selected by the designer; $\mu_i(t)$ is the performance function can be described as

$$\mu_i(t) = (\mu_{i0} - \mu_{i\infty}) e^{-\kappa_i t} + \mu_{i\infty} \quad (30)$$

where $\mu_{i0} > \mu_{i\infty}$ and $\kappa_i > 0$ are design parameters. From (29) we know that $\bar{\delta}_i \mu_{i0}$ defines the upper bound of the maximum overshoot and $-\underline{\delta}_i \mu_{i0}$ defines the lower bound of the undershoot, $\mu_{i\infty}$ denotes the allowable steady state tracking error. To solve the control problem with prescribed performance (29), we introduce the transformed error $\xi_{i1} \in \mathfrak{R}, i = 1, \dots, N$, which satisfy the following equation

$$\xi_{i1} = \operatorname{atanh} \left(\left(\frac{e_{i1}(t)}{\mu_i(t)} - \frac{\bar{\delta}_i - \underline{\delta}_i}{2} \right) / \frac{\bar{\delta}_i + \underline{\delta}_i}{2} \right) \quad (31)$$

where $\operatorname{atanh}(\cdot)$ denotes the inverse hyperbolic tangent function. From (31) we get

$$e_{i1}(t) = \mu_i(t) \left(\tanh(\xi_{i1}) \frac{\bar{\delta}_i + \underline{\delta}_i}{2} + \frac{\bar{\delta}_i - \underline{\delta}_i}{2} \right) \quad (32)$$

where $\tanh(\cdot)$ denotes the hyperbolic tangent function, it has the following properties

- 1) $-\underline{\delta}_i < \tanh(\xi_{i1}) < \bar{\delta}_i, \forall \xi_{i1} \in L_\infty$
- 2) $\lim_{\xi_{i1} \rightarrow +\infty} \tanh(\xi_{i1}) = \bar{\delta}_i; \lim_{\xi_{i1} \rightarrow -\infty} \tanh(\xi_{i1}) = \underline{\delta}_i$

Note that PPF (30), the associated parameters $\bar{\delta}_i, \underline{\delta}_i, \kappa_i, \mu_{i0}$ and $\mu_{i\infty}$ are all a priori designed. For any initial condition $e_{i1}(0)$, if parameters $\bar{\delta}_i, \mu_{i0}$ and $\underline{\delta}_i$ are selected such that $-\underline{\delta}_i \mu_i(0) < e_{i1}(0) < \bar{\delta}_i \mu_i(0)$ and ξ_{i1} can be controlled to be bounded (i.e., $\xi_{i1} \in L_\infty, \forall t > 0$), then $-\underline{\delta}_i < \tanh(\xi_{i1}) < \bar{\delta}_i$ holds; thus, the condition $-\underline{\delta}_i \mu_i(t) < e_{i1}(t) < \bar{\delta}_i \mu_i(t)$ is guaranteed. Consequently, the tracking control problem of system (88) is now transformed to stabilize the transformed system (31). Define the following tracking errors estimations for the i^{th} subsystem as follow:

$$\hat{e}_{i1}(t) = y_i(t) - y_{id}(t) \quad (33)$$

$$\hat{e}_{i1}^{(n_i+1)} = \dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - y_{id}^{(n_i+1)} \quad (34)$$

Let the transformed error estimations be defined by:

$$\hat{\xi}_{i1} = \operatorname{atanh} \left(\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{i1}(t)}{\mu_i(t)} - \frac{\bar{\delta}_i - \underline{\delta}_i}{2} \right) / \frac{\bar{\delta}_i + \underline{\delta}_i}{2} \right) \quad (35)$$

Then, from (35), the transformed error $\hat{\xi}_i$ is derived as

$$\dot{\hat{\xi}}_{i1} = \varphi_i \left[\dot{\hat{e}}_{i1} - \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i} \right] = \varphi_i \dot{\hat{e}}_{i1} + \gamma_1^i(\hat{e}_{i1}, t) \quad (36)$$

where $\gamma_1^i(\hat{e}_{i1}, t) = -\varphi_i \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i}$ and

$\varphi_i = \frac{(\bar{\delta}_i + \underline{\delta}_i)/2}{\mu_i(\bar{\delta}_i + \hat{e}_{i1}/\mu_i)(\underline{\delta}_i + \hat{e}_{i1}/\mu_i)}$ can be calculated based on $\hat{e}_{i1}(t)$ and $\mu_i(t)$, and fulfills

$0 < \varphi_i < \varphi_{iM} = ((\underline{\delta}_i + \bar{\delta}_i) / \mu_{i\infty} \bar{\delta}_i \underline{\delta}_i)$.

Moreover, one may obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\hat{\xi}}_{i1} &= \varphi_i \left[\ddot{\hat{e}}_{i1} - \frac{\dot{\hat{e}}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i} - \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \ddot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i} + \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i^2}{\mu_i^2} \right] \\ &+ \dot{\varphi}_i \left[\dot{\hat{e}}_{i1} - \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i} \right] \\ &= \varphi_i \ddot{\hat{e}}_{i1} + \gamma_2^i(\hat{e}_{i1}, \dot{\hat{e}}_{i1}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

where

$\gamma_2^i(\hat{e}_{i1}, \dot{\hat{e}}_{i1}, t) = \varphi_i \left[-\frac{\dot{\hat{e}}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i} - \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \ddot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i} + \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i^2}{\mu_i^2} \right] + \dot{\varphi}_i \left[\dot{\hat{e}}_{i1} - \frac{\hat{e}_{i1} \dot{\mu}_i}{\mu_i} \right]$. By a similar way, we can obtain the k -derivatives $k = 1, \dots, (n_i + 1)$ of $\hat{\xi}_{i1}^{(k)}$ as follows

$$\hat{\xi}_{i1}^{(k)} = \varphi_i \hat{e}_{i1}^{(n_i+1)} + \gamma_k^i(\hat{e}_{i1}, \dot{\hat{e}}_{i1}, \dots, \hat{e}_{i1}^{(k-1)}, t) \quad (38)$$

Define the filtered error as

$$\hat{e}_{is} = [\Lambda_i^T \mathbf{1}] \left[\hat{\xi}_{i1}, \dot{\hat{\xi}}_{i1}, \dots, \hat{\xi}_{i1}^{(n_i)} \right]^T \quad (39)$$

where $\Lambda_i = [\lambda_{i1}, \dots, \lambda_{in_i-1}]^T$ is properly chosen such that $s^{n_i} + \lambda_{in_i-1}s^{n_i-1} + \dots + \lambda_{i0}$ is Hurwitz. From (39) we get

$$\dot{\hat{e}}_{is} = [0, \Lambda_i^T] \left[\hat{\xi}_{i1}, \dot{\hat{\xi}}_{i1}, \dots, \hat{\xi}_{i1}^{(n_i)} \right]^T + \hat{\xi}_{i1}^{(n_i+1)} \quad (40)$$

Using (36)-(38) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= [0, \Lambda_i^T] \left[\hat{\xi}_{i1}, \dot{\hat{\xi}}_{i1}, \dots, \hat{\xi}_{i1}^{(n_i)} \right]^T + \varphi_i \hat{e}_{i1}^{(n_i+1)} \\ &+ \gamma_{n_i}^i(\hat{e}_{i1}, \dot{\hat{e}}_{i1}, \dots, \hat{e}_{i1}^{(n_i)}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

We have $\hat{e}_{i1}^{(n_i+1)} = \dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - y_{id}^{(n_i+1)}$, then by using (23) and (41), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= \vartheta_i + \varphi_i [F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) \dot{u}_i^f] \\ &+ \varphi_i (\dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i,n_i+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where $\vartheta_i = [0, \Lambda_i^T] [\hat{\xi}_{i1}, \dot{\xi}_{i1}, \dots, \hat{\xi}_{i1}^{(n_i)}]^T + \gamma_{n_i}^i (\hat{e}_{i1}, \dot{e}_{i1}, \dots, \hat{e}_{i1}^{(n_i)}, t) - \varphi_i y_{id}^{(n_i+1)}$

Substituting faults and saturation models (4) and (8) into (42) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= \varphi_i [F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) (\dot{v}_i + \Delta \dot{u}_i + \dot{f}_{ai})] \\ &+ \vartheta_i + \varphi_i (\dot{\hat{z}}_{i, n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i, n_i+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Let define $F_{ai}(X, u_i^f) = G_i(X, u_i^f) \dot{f}_{ai}$, one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= \varphi_i [F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) \dot{v}_i \\ &+ F_{ai}(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i] \\ &+ \vartheta_i + \varphi_i (\dot{\hat{z}}_{i, n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i, n_i+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Then, let the signal v_i be generated by

$$\dot{v}_i = \omega_i \quad (45)$$

Now, the equation (44) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= \varphi_i [F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) \omega_i \\ &+ F_{ai}(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i] \\ &+ \vartheta_i + \varphi_i (\dot{\hat{z}}_{i, n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i, n_i+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

Consider the following NNs approximations of the i^{th} row of unknown vector function $F_i(X, u_i^f)$ and the unknown actuator faults $F_{ai}(X, u_i^f)$ as follows

$$\varphi_i F_i(X, u_i^f) + \vartheta_i = W_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) + \varepsilon_{ic}(Z_{ic}) \quad (47)$$

$$\varphi_i F_{ai}(X, u_i^f) = W_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) + \varepsilon_{ia}(Z_{ia}) \quad (48)$$

where W_{ic} and W_{ia} are ideal parameter vectors, which are introduced only for analysis purpose, and their values are not needed when implementing the controller, and $S_{ic}(\cdot)$ are NNs vectors fixed a priori by the designer, $\varepsilon_{ic}(Z_{ic})$ and $\varepsilon_{ia}(Z_{ia})$ are the minimum approximation errors, and the input vectors are $Z_{ic} = [X, \varphi_i, \vartheta_i, u_i^f]^T$ and $Z_{ia} = [X, \varphi_i, u_i^f]^T$, respectively. Substituting (47) and (48) into (44) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= [W_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) + W_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) \\ &+ \varphi_i G_i(X, u_i^f) \dot{v}_i + \varphi_i G_i(X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i \\ &+ \mathcal{U}_i] + \varphi_i (\dot{\hat{z}}_{i, n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i, n_i+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

where $\mathcal{U}_i = \varepsilon_{ic}(Z_{ic}) + \varepsilon_{ia}(Z_{ia})$.

Remark 1. Since the approximation errors $\varepsilon_{ic}(Z_{ic})$ and $\varepsilon_{ia}(Z_{ia})$, are small and bounded due to the universel approximation theorem, then, there exist unknown positive constants $\bar{\tau}_i$ such that

$$|\mathcal{U}_i| \leq \bar{\tau}_i \quad (50)$$

where each element of the unknown parameters in \mathcal{U}_i is bounded.

3.4. Adaptive NNs Controller

In this study, we propose the following NNs dynamic control laws to achieve the control objective:

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_i &= \frac{N(\zeta_i)}{\varphi_i} (\hat{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) + \hat{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia})) \\ &+ \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) + \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i)\end{aligned}\quad (51)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\zeta}_i &= \hat{e}_{is} (\hat{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) + \hat{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia})) \\ &+ \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) + \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i)\end{aligned}\quad (52)$$

and the corresponding adaptive laws as follows

$$\dot{\hat{W}}_{i0} = \Gamma_{i0} (\tilde{z}_{i1} S_{i0}(Z_{i0}) - \sigma_{i0} \hat{W}_{i0}) \quad (53)$$

$$\dot{\hat{W}}_{ic} = \Gamma_{ic} (\hat{e}_{is} S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) - \sigma_{ic} \hat{W}_{ic}) \quad (54)$$

$$\dot{\hat{W}}_{ia} = \Gamma_{ia} (\hat{e}_{is} S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) - \sigma_{ia} \hat{W}_{ia}) \quad (55)$$

$$\dot{\hat{\tau}}_i = \gamma_i \left(-\hat{e}_{is} \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) + \sigma_{i2} \hat{\tau}_i \right) \quad (56)$$

where $\Gamma_{i0} = \Gamma_{ic} = \Gamma_{ia} > 0$, $\gamma_i > 0$, $\sigma_{i0} = \sigma_{ic} = \sigma_{ia} = \sigma_{i2} \geq 0$, $\alpha_i > 0$, ϵ_i, χ_i are positive constants, $\hat{\tau}_i$ is the estimate of the unknown parameter τ_i .

Subject to actuator saturation, we introduce the auxiliary compensator as follows:

$$\dot{\chi}_i = \begin{cases} -k_{ie} \chi_i - \frac{\bar{g} \varphi_i M |\hat{e}_{is} \Delta \dot{u}_i| + 0.5 \Delta \dot{u}_i^2}{\chi_i^2} \chi_i + \Delta \dot{u}_i & \text{if } |\chi_i| \geq \eta_{i,0} \\ 0 & \text{if } |\chi_i| < \eta_{i,0} \end{cases} \quad (57)$$

with $\Delta \dot{u}_i = \frac{dh(v_i)}{dv_i} \omega_i - \omega_i + \dot{\Upsilon}(v_i)$; $\eta_{i,0}$ is a small positive constant and $k_{ie} > 0$ is a design parameter. Based on some mathematical manipulations, then, by adding and subtracting $\hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right)$ and $\alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i)$ to the equation (49) one obtains

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= [\hat{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) - \tilde{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) + \hat{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) \\ &- \tilde{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) + \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) - \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) \\ &+ \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i) - \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i) + \varphi_i G_i(X, u_i^f) \omega_i \\ &+ \varphi_i G_i(X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i + \mathcal{U}_i] \\ &+ (\dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i,n_i+1})\end{aligned}\quad (58)$$

where $W_{ic} = \hat{W}_{ic} - \tilde{W}_{ic}$, $W_{ia} = \hat{W}_{ia} - \tilde{W}_{ia}$ and $\tilde{\tau}_i = \bar{\tau}_i - \hat{\tau}_i$. By replacing the proposed adaptive control law (51) into (58), one can find the following result.

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= [-\tilde{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) - \tilde{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) \\
&\quad - \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) - \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i) \\
&\quad + (\hat{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) + \hat{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) \\
&\quad + \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) + \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i)) \\
&\quad \times \left(1 + G_i(X, u_i^f) N(\zeta_i)\right) \\
&\quad + \varphi_i G_i(X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i + \mathcal{U}_i] \\
&\quad + \left(\dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i,n_i+1}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

Multiplying \hat{e}_{is} to (57) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{e}_{is} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} &= \hat{e}_{is} [-\tilde{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic}(Z_{ic}) - \tilde{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia}(Z_{ia}) \\
&\quad - \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) - \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i) \\
&\quad + \varphi_i G_i(X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i + \mathcal{U}_i] \\
&\quad + \left(1 + G_i(X, u_i^f) N(\zeta_i)\right) \dot{\zeta}_i \\
&\quad + \hat{e}_{is} \varphi_i \left(\dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i,n_i+1}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

Noting that $\tilde{z}_i = [\hat{z}_{i1} - z_{i1}, \dots, \hat{z}_{i,n_i+1} - z_{i,n_i+1}]^T$, then

$$\hat{e}_{is} \varphi_i \left(\dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i,n_i+1}\right) = \Psi_{in} \dot{\tilde{z}}_i \tag{61}$$

with $\Psi_{in} = [0, 0, \dots, \hat{e}_{is} \varphi_i]$.

Subtracting (25) from (24), we get the dynamics of the observation errors as

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{\tilde{z}}_i &= (A_i - \underline{k}_{i0} C_i^T) \tilde{z}_i + P_i^{-1} C_i^T \hat{W}_{i0}^T S_i(Z_i) \\
&\quad - B_i [F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) \dot{v}_i + k_{ic}^T \hat{z}_i] \\
\tilde{z}_{i1} &= C^T \tilde{z}_i
\end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

To facilitate the controller design, an NN is used to approximate the following unknown nonlinear functions, such as

$$F_i(X, u_i^f) + G_i(X, u_i^f) \dot{v}_i + k_{ic}^T \hat{z}_i = W_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_{i0}) + \varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0}) \tag{63}$$

where W_{0i} is the ideal parameter vector, which is introduced only for analysis purposes, and its value is not needed when implementing the controller, and $S_i(\cdot)$ is the NN activation function fixed a priori by the designer, $\varepsilon_{0i}(Z)$ is the NN approximation error, and the input vector is $Z_{i0} = [X, k_{ic}^T \hat{z}_i, \dot{v}_i(t), u_i(v_i(t))]^T$, since the ideal parameter vectors W_{i0} are unknown, they should be estimated by suitable adaptation laws. The estimates are represented by \hat{W}_{i0} where $\tilde{W}_{i0} = \hat{W}_{i0} - W_{i0}$. Substituting (63) into (62) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{\tilde{z}}_i &= \bar{A}_{i0} \tilde{z}_i + P_i^{-1} C_i^T \left[\tilde{W}_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_{i0}) + W_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_i) \right] \\
&\quad - B_i [W_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_{i0}) + \varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0})] \\
\tilde{z}_{i1} &= C^T \tilde{z}_i
\end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

Substituting (64) into (61), we have

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{e}_{is}\varphi_i\left(\dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i,n_i+1}\right) &= \Psi_{in}P_i^{-1}C_i^T\tilde{W}_{i0}^TS_{i0}(Z_{i0}) \\ &+ \Psi_{in}\bar{A}_{i0}\tilde{z}_i + \Psi_{in}B_{iw}\end{aligned}\quad (65)$$

where $B_{iw} = P_i^{-1}C_i^TW_{i0}^TS_{i0}(Z_{i0}) - B_i[W_{i0}^TS_{i0}(Z_{i0}) + \varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0})]$

By using Young's inequality, we obtain

$$\Psi_{in}\bar{A}_{i0}\tilde{z}_i \leq \frac{1}{2}\|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{z}_i^T\bar{A}_{i0}^T\bar{A}_{i0}\tilde{z}_i \quad (66)$$

Since the NNs activation function is bounded, we have that $\|S_{i0}(Z_{i0})\| \leq \bar{\omega}_{s0}$, with $\bar{\omega}_{s0} \in \mathfrak{R}^+$. Then, from (16) we know that the minimum approximation errors $\varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0})$ are bounded, and notice that NNs activation function $S_{i0}(Z_{i0})$ is bounded, using Assumption 3 we can conclude that $(W_{i0}^TS_{i0}(Z_{i0}) + \varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0}))^2$ and $(W_{i0}^TS_{i0}(Z_i))^2$ are bounded, then there exists a constant \bar{B}_{iw} , such that $\frac{1}{2}\|B_{iw}\|^2 \leq \bar{B}_{iw}$ using Young's inequality, we have

$$\Psi_{in}B_{iw} \leq \frac{1}{2}\|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\|B_{iw}\|^2 \leq \frac{1}{2}\|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \bar{B}_{iw} \quad (67)$$

$$\Psi_{in}P_i^{-1}C_i^T\tilde{W}_{i0}^TS_i(Z_i) \leq \frac{1}{2}\|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \frac{\|W_{i0}^T\|^2}{2}\bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 \quad (68)$$

Substituting (66),(67) and (68) into (65), one obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{e}_{is}\varphi_i\left(\dot{\hat{z}}_{i,n_i+1} - \dot{z}_{i,n_i+1}\right) &\leq \frac{1}{2}\tilde{z}_i^T\bar{A}_{i0}^T\bar{A}_{i0}\tilde{z}_i + \frac{\|w_{i0}^T\|^2}{2}\bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 \\ &+ \frac{3}{2}\|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \bar{B}_{iw}\end{aligned}\quad (69)$$

Substituting (69) into (60), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\hat{e}}_{is}\dot{e}_{is} &= \hat{e}_{is}[-\tilde{W}_{ic}^TS_{ic}(Z_{ic}) - \tilde{W}_{ia}^TS_{ia}(Z_{ia}) \\ &- \hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) - \alpha_i(\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i) \\ &+ \varphi_i G_i(X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i + \mathcal{U}_i] \\ &+ \left(1 + G_i(X, u_i^f) N(\zeta_i)\right) \dot{\zeta}_i \\ &+ \frac{1}{2}\tilde{z}_i^T\bar{A}_{i0}^T\bar{A}_{i0}\tilde{z}_i + \frac{\|w_{i0}^T\|^2}{2}\bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 \\ &+ \frac{3}{2}\|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \bar{B}_{iw}\end{aligned}\quad (70)$$

3.5. Stability analysis

According to the above discussions, the following theorem discloses the stability of the closed-loop system.

Theorem: Consider the uncertain MIMO pure feedback nonlinear system (88) with input saturation, output constraints and actuator faults under Assumptions 1 – 3 and the observer (25). Then, the proposed fault tolerant adaptive controller, defined by (53)-(56), guarantees the following properties:

1. All signals of the closed-loop system are bounded;
2. The tracking errors satisfies $-\delta_i\mu_i(t) < e_{i1}(t) < \bar{\delta}_i\mu_i(t)$.

Proof. Define the following Lyapunov function candidate

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i &= \frac{1}{2} \tilde{z}_i^T P_i \tilde{z}_i + \frac{1}{2} \hat{e}_{is}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{W}_{i0}^T \Gamma_{i0}^{-1} \tilde{W}_{i0} + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{W}_{ic}^T \Gamma_{ic}^{-1} \tilde{W}_{ic} \\
&+ \frac{1}{2} \tilde{W}_{ia}^T \Gamma_{ia}^{-1} \tilde{W}_{ia} + \frac{1}{2\gamma_i} \tilde{\tau}_i^2 + \frac{1}{2} \chi_i^2
\end{aligned} \tag{71}$$

The time derivative of V_i is given as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{V}_i &= \frac{1}{2} (\dot{\tilde{z}}_i^T P_i \tilde{z}_i + \tilde{z}_i^T P_i \dot{\tilde{z}}_i) + \hat{e}_{is} \dot{\hat{e}}_{is} + \tilde{W}_{i0}^T \Gamma_{i0}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{i0} \\
&+ \tilde{W}_{ic}^T \Gamma_{ic}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{ic} + \tilde{W}_{ia}^T \Gamma_{ia}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{ia} \\
&+ \frac{1}{\gamma_i} \dot{\tilde{\tau}}_i \hat{\tau}_i + \chi_i \dot{\chi}_i
\end{aligned} \tag{72}$$

Then, by substituting (70) and (64) into (72), we can get

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{V}_i &= \frac{1}{2} \tilde{z}_i^T (\bar{A}_{i0}^T P_i + P_i \bar{A}_{i0}) \tilde{z}_i + \tilde{z}_i C_i^T \tilde{W}_{i0}^T S_{i0} (Z_{i0}) \\
&+ \tilde{z}_i C_i^T W_{i0}^T S_{i0} (Z_{i0}) + \tilde{z}_i B_{i\theta} - \hat{e}_{is} \tilde{W}_{ic}^T S_{ic} (Z_{ic}) \\
&- \hat{e}_{is} \tilde{W}_{ia}^T S_{ia} (Z_{ia}) - \hat{e}_{is} \hat{t}_i \tanh \left(\frac{e_{is}}{\epsilon_i} \right) + \hat{e}_{is} \mathcal{U}_i \\
&- \hat{e}_{is} \alpha_i (\hat{e}_{is} - \chi_i) + \hat{e}_{is} \varphi_i G_i (X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i \\
&+ \left(1 + G_i (X, u_i^f) N(\zeta_i) \right) \dot{\zeta}_i + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{z}_i^T \bar{A}_{i0}^T \bar{A}_{i0} \tilde{z}_i \\
&+ \frac{\|w_{i0}^T\|^2}{2} \bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 + \frac{3}{2} \|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \bar{B}_{iw} + \tilde{W}_{i0}^T \Gamma_{i0}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{i0} \\
&+ \tilde{W}_{ic}^T \Gamma_{ic}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{ic} + \tilde{W}_{ia}^T \Gamma_{ia}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{ia} \\
&+ \frac{1}{\gamma_i} \dot{\tilde{\tau}}_i \hat{\tau}_i + \chi_i \dot{\chi}_i
\end{aligned} \tag{73}$$

where $B_{i\theta} = -P_i B_i [W_{i0}^T S_{i0} (Z_{i0}) + \epsilon_{i0} (Z_{i0})]$.

By substituting (26) and the auxiliary system (57) into (73) results in

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{V}_i &\leq -\frac{1}{2} \tilde{z}_i^T (Q_i + \bar{A}_{i0}^T \bar{A}_{i0}) \tilde{z}_i - \hat{e}_{is} \hat{t}_i \tanh \left(\frac{e_{is}}{\epsilon_i} \right) \\
&+ \left(1 + G_i (X, u_i^f) N(\zeta_i) \right) \dot{\zeta}_i + \hat{e}_{is} \mathcal{U}_i - \alpha_i \hat{e}_{is}^2 \\
&+ \alpha_i \hat{e}_{is} \chi_i + \hat{e}_{is} \varphi_i G_i (X, u_i^f) \Delta \dot{u}_i - k_{ie} \chi_i^2 \\
&- \varphi_i M \bar{g} |\hat{e}_{is} \Delta \dot{u}_i| - 0.5 \Delta \dot{u}_i^2 + \chi_i \Delta \dot{u}_i \\
&+ \tilde{W}_{i0}^T \left(-\tilde{z}_{i1} S_{i0} (Z_{i0}) + \Gamma_{i0}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{i0} \right) \\
&+ \tilde{W}_{ic}^T \left(-\hat{e}_{is} S_{ic} (Z_{ic}) + \Gamma_{ic}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{ic} \right) \\
&+ \tilde{W}_{ia}^T \left(-\hat{e}_{is} S_{ia} (Z_{ia}) + \Gamma_{ia}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{W}}_{ia} \right) \\
&+ \frac{1}{\gamma_i} \dot{\tilde{\tau}}_i \hat{\tau}_i + \tilde{z}_i C_i^T W_{i0}^T S_{i0} (Z_{i0}) + \tilde{z}_i B_{i\theta} \\
&+ \frac{\|w_{i0}^T\|^2}{2} \bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 + \frac{3}{2} \|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \bar{B}_{iw}
\end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{e}_{is}\mathcal{U}_i &- \hat{e}_{is}\hat{\tau}_i \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) \leq |\hat{e}_{is}|\bar{\tau}_i \\
&+ \hat{e}_{is}|\bar{\tau}_i - \tilde{\tau}_i| \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right) \\
&\leq \kappa\epsilon_i\bar{\tau}_i + \tilde{\tau}_i\hat{e}_{is} \tanh\left(\frac{\hat{e}_{is}}{\epsilon_i}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{75}$$

$$\hat{e}_{is}\varphi_i G_i \Delta \dot{u}_i - \varphi_i M \bar{g} |\hat{e}_{is} \Delta \dot{u}_i| \leq 0 \tag{76}$$

$$-0.5\Delta \dot{u}_i^2 + \chi_i \Delta \dot{u}_i \leq 0.5\chi_i^2 \tag{77}$$

$$\hat{e}_{is}\alpha_i\chi_i \leq \frac{\alpha_i}{2}\chi_i^2 + \frac{\alpha_i}{2}\hat{e}_{is}^2 \tag{78}$$

since the NNs activation function is bounded, we have that $\|S_{i0}(Z_i)\| \leq \bar{\omega}_{s0}$, with $\bar{\omega}_{s0} \in \mathfrak{R}^+$. Noting $B_{i\theta} = -P_i B_i [W_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_i) + \varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0})]$, by using $2\gamma^T \beta \leq \|\gamma\|^2 + \|\beta\|^2$, one has

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{z}_i C_i^T W_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_i) &\leq \frac{\|\tilde{z}_i\|^2 \|C_i^T\|^2}{2\alpha_0} + \frac{\alpha_0 \|W_{i0}^T\|^2}{2} \bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 \\
&\leq \frac{\|\tilde{z}_i\|^2}{2\alpha_0} + \frac{\alpha_0 \|W_{i0}^T\|^2}{2} \bar{\omega}_{s0}^2
\end{aligned} \tag{79}$$

where $\|C_i^T\|^2 = 1$.

$$\tilde{z}_i B_{i\theta} \leq \frac{\|\tilde{z}_i\|^2}{2\beta_0} + \frac{\beta_0 \|B_{i\theta}\|^2}{2} \tag{80}$$

where $\alpha_0 > 0, \beta_0 > 0$. Then, from the property of the universal approximation we know that the minimum approximation errors $\varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0})$ are bounded, and notice that NNs activation function $S_{i0}(Z_i)$ is bounded, using Assumption 2 we know that $(W_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_i) + \varepsilon_{i0}(Z_{i0}))^2$ and $(W_{i0}^T S_{i0}(Z_i))^2$ are bounded, then there exists a constant $\bar{B}_{i\theta}$ such that

$$\frac{\alpha_0 \|W_{i0}^T\|^2}{2} \bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 + \frac{\beta_0 \|B_{i\theta}\|^2}{2} \leq \bar{B}_{i\theta}$$

According to the above inequalities and the parameter adaptation laws (53)-(56), one has

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{V}_i &\leq -\frac{1}{2}\lambda \|\tilde{z}_i\|^2 - \frac{\alpha_i}{2}\hat{e}_{is}^2 - \left(k_{ie} - \frac{\alpha_i}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\right)\chi_i^2 \\
&+ \left(1 + \bar{G}_i(X, u_i^f) N(\zeta_i)\right) \dot{\zeta}_i \\
&- \sigma_{i0} \tilde{W}_{i0}^T \hat{W}_{i0} - \sigma_{ic} \tilde{W}_{ic}^T \hat{W}_{ic} - \sigma_{ia} \tilde{W}_{ia}^T \hat{W}_{ia} \\
&+ \sigma_{i2} \tilde{\tau}_i \hat{\tau}_i + \kappa\epsilon_i \bar{\tau}_i + \frac{\|W_{i0}^T\|^2}{2} \bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 + \frac{3}{2} \|\Psi_{in}\|^2 \\
&+ \bar{B}_{iw} + \bar{B}_{i\theta}
\end{aligned} \tag{81}$$

where $\lambda = \lambda_{\min}(Q) - \frac{1}{\alpha_0} - \frac{1}{\beta_0} > 0$, with $\lambda_{\min}(Q)$ being the minimum eigenvalue of the matrix Q , and the design parameters are chosen to satisfy conditions $\alpha_i > 0$ and $k_{ie} - \frac{\alpha_i}{2} - \frac{1}{2} > 0$. By completion of squares, we have

$$-\sigma_{i0} \tilde{W}_{i0}^T \hat{W}_{i0} \leq \frac{\sigma_{i0}}{2} \|W_{i0}\|^2 - \frac{\sigma_{i0}}{2} \|\tilde{W}_{i0}\|^2 \tag{82}$$

$$-\sigma_{ic}\tilde{W}_{ic}^T\hat{W}_{ic} \leq \frac{\sigma_{ic}}{2}\|W_{ic}\|^2 - \frac{\sigma_{ic}}{2}\|\tilde{W}_{ic}\|^2 \quad (83)$$

$$-\sigma_{ia}\tilde{W}_{ia}^T\hat{W}_{ia} \leq \frac{\sigma_{ia}}{2}\|W_{ia}\|^2 - \frac{\sigma_{ia}}{2}\|\tilde{W}_{ia}\|^2 \quad (84)$$

$$\sigma_{i2}\tilde{\tau}_i\hat{\tau}_i \leq \frac{\sigma_{i2}}{2}\bar{\tau}_2^2 - \frac{\sigma_{i2}}{2}\tilde{\tau}_2^2 \quad (85)$$

with (82)-(84) we can rewrite (81) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_i &\leq -\frac{1}{2}\lambda\|\tilde{z}_i\|^2 - \frac{\alpha_i}{2}\hat{e}_{is}^2 - \left(k_{ie} - \frac{\alpha_i}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\right)\chi_i^2 \\ &\quad + \left(1 + G_i(X, u_i^f)N(\zeta_i)\right)\dot{\zeta}_i \\ &\quad - \frac{\sigma_{i0}}{2}\|\tilde{W}_{i0}\|^2 - \frac{\sigma_{ic}}{2}\|\tilde{W}_{ic}\|^2 - \frac{\sigma_{ia}}{2}\|\tilde{W}_{ia}\|^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{\sigma_{i2}}{2}\tilde{\tau}_2^2 + \frac{\sigma_{i0}}{2}\|W_{i0}\|^2 + \frac{\sigma_{ic}}{2}\|W_{ic}\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2}\|W_{ia}\|^2(\bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 + \sigma_{ia}) + \frac{\sigma_{i2}}{2}\bar{\tau}_2^2 \\ &\quad + \kappa\epsilon_i\bar{\tau}_i + \frac{3}{2}\|\Psi_{in}\|^2 + \bar{B}_{iw} + \bar{B}_{i\theta} \\ &\leq -c_{i1}V_i + c_{i0} + \left(1 + G_i(x_i, u_i^f)N(\zeta_i)\right)\zeta_i \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} c_{i1} &= \min\left\{\frac{\lambda}{\lambda_{\max}(P_i)}, \frac{1}{2}\left(\alpha_i - \frac{1}{2}\right), \frac{1}{2}\left(k_{ie} - \frac{\alpha_i}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\right), \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{\sigma_{i0}}{\lambda_{\max}(r_{i0}^{-1})}, \frac{\sigma_{ic}}{\lambda_{\max}(r_{ic}^{-1})}, \frac{\sigma_{ia}}{\lambda_{\max}(r_{ia}^{-1})}, \sigma_{i2}\gamma_i\right\}, \\ c_{i0} &= \frac{\sigma_{i0}}{2}\|W_{i0}\|^2 + \frac{\sigma_{ic}}{2}\|W_{ic}\|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\|W_{ia}\|^2(\bar{\omega}_{s0}^2 + \sigma_{ia}) \\ &\quad + \frac{\sigma_{i2}}{2}\bar{\tau}_2^2 + \kappa\bar{\tau}_i + \frac{3}{2}\|\psi_{in}\|^2 + \bar{B}_{iw} + \bar{B}_{i\theta} \end{aligned}$$

and $\lambda_{\max}(P_i)$, $\lambda_{\max}(\Gamma_{i0}^{-1})$, $\lambda_{\max}(\Gamma_{ic}^{-1})$ and $\lambda_{\max}(\Gamma_{ia}^{-1})$ denote the maximum eigenvalues of P_i and Γ_{i0}^{-1} , Γ_{ic}^{-1} and Γ_{ia}^{-1} , respectively. Then, integrating both sides of (86) yields

$$V_i(t) \leq \bar{c}_0 + e^{c_1 t} \int_0^t (1 + G_i(\cdot)N(\zeta_i(\tau)))\dot{\zeta}_i(\tau)e^{c_1\tau}d\tau \quad (87)$$

where $\bar{c}_0 = V_i(0) + c_{i0}/c_{i1}$. From Lemma 2 of [33], $V(t)$, $\zeta_i(t)$ and $\int_0^t G_i(\cdot)N(\zeta_i(\tau))\dot{\zeta}_i(\tau)$ are bounded in $[0, t_f)$. Therefore, the boundedness of the solution of the closed-loop system ensures $t_f = \infty$. Thus, all the signals of the closed-loop system are bounded. Then, there exists a constant c_{i2} such that

$|e^{c_1 t} \int_0^t (1 + G_i(\cdot)N(\zeta_i(\tau)))\dot{\zeta}_i(\tau)e^{c_1\tau}d\tau| + \bar{c}_0 < c_{i2}$. From (87) and the definitions of V_i , the estimation error \tilde{z}_i can be shown to satisfy $\frac{1}{2}\tilde{z}_i^T P_i \tilde{z}_i \leq (V|_{t=0} + c_{i0}/c_{i1} + c_{i2})$ and converges exponentially to the compact set

$$\Omega_{\tilde{z}_i} = \left\{\tilde{z}_i \in \mathfrak{R} \mid \|\tilde{z}_i\| \leq \sqrt{\Omega/\lambda_{\min}(P_i)}\right\},$$

with

$$\Omega = 2(V|_{t=0} + c_{i0}/c_{i1} + c_{i2})$$

can be made sufficiently small by choosing the design parameters appropriately. Consequently, the parameter estimate errors \hat{e}_{is} , \tilde{W}_{i0} , \tilde{W}_{ic} , \tilde{W}_{ia} , $\tilde{\tau}_i$ and χ_i are also bounded, and remain in the compact sets

$$\Omega_{\hat{e}_{is}}, \Omega_{\tilde{W}_{i0}}, \Omega_{\tilde{W}_{ic}}, \Omega_{\tilde{W}_{ia}}, \Omega_{\tilde{\tau}_i} \text{ and } \Omega_{\chi_i} \text{ in the sense that } \Omega_{\tilde{e}_{is}} = \left\{\tilde{e}_{is} \in \mathfrak{R} \mid \|\tilde{e}_{is}\| \leq \sqrt{\Omega}\right\},$$

$$\Omega_{\tilde{W}_{i0}} = \left\{\tilde{W}_{i0} \in \mathfrak{R} \mid \|\tilde{W}_{i0}\| \leq \sqrt{\Omega/\lambda_{\min}(\Gamma_{i0}^{-1})}\right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_{\tilde{W}_{ic}} &= \left\{ \tilde{W}_{ic} \in \mathfrak{R} \mid \|\tilde{W}_{ic}\| \leq \sqrt{\Omega/\lambda_{\min}(\Gamma_{ic}^{-1})} \right\} \\ \Omega_{\tilde{W}_{ia}} &= \left\{ \tilde{W}_{ia} \in \mathfrak{R} \mid \|\tilde{W}_{ia}\| \leq \sqrt{\Omega/\lambda_{\min}(\Gamma_{ia}^{-1})} \right\} \\ \Omega_{\tilde{\tau}_i} &= \left\{ \tilde{\tau}_i \in \mathfrak{R} \mid \|\tilde{\tau}_i\| \leq \sqrt{\gamma_i \Omega} \right\} \\ \Omega_{\chi_i} &= \left\{ \chi_i \in \mathfrak{R} \mid \|\chi_i\| \leq \sqrt{\Omega} \right\}\end{aligned}$$

From the boundedness of $\tilde{z}_i, \tilde{W}_{i0}, \tilde{W}_{ia}, \tilde{W}_{ic}, \tilde{\tau}_i$ and χ_i one can directly conclude about the boundedness of $\hat{z}_i, z_i, e_{is}, \hat{W}_{i0}, \hat{W}_{ia}, \hat{W}_{ic}$ and $\hat{\tau}_i$ since $\tilde{e}_i = e_i - \hat{e}_i = \tilde{z}_i, \hat{W}_{i0} = \tilde{W}_{i0} - W_{i0}, \hat{W}_{ic} = \tilde{W}_{ic} - W_{ic}, \hat{W}_{ia} = \tilde{W}_{ia} - W_{ia}, \hat{\tau}_i = \tilde{\tau}_i - \tau_i$ and the ideal parameters W_{i0}, W_{ic}, W_{ia} and τ_i must be bounded. In addition, from the properties of the transformation function, we conclude that the tracking error $\xi_i(t)$ is able to guarantee the output constraints described by (29) for all $t \geq 0$. The state x_{i1} is bounded because $x_{i1} = z_{i1}$. Furthermore, since z_{i2} is bounded and $\partial\varphi_{i2}(\bar{x}_{i2})/\partial x_{i2} > 0$, and based on the definition of $z_{i2} = \varphi_{i2}(\bar{x}_{i2})$, we conclude that x_{i2} is bounded. In the same way, we conclude that all the states $x_{ij}, j = 1, \dots, n_i + 1; i = 3, \dots, N$ are bounded.

4. SIMULATIONS RUSELTS

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed distributed control law, simulation studies have been conducted on two distinct examples. The first illustrates a theoretical pure-feedback nonlinear system, while the second involves a real-world UAV quadrotor. Combined, these case studies provide a comprehensive evaluation of the strategy's practical applicability and confirm its performance in both theoretical and real-world scenarios.

Example 1

Consider a mathematical pure-feedback nonlinear system that is affected by actuator faults, external disturbances, and input saturation. The dynamics are modeled by the following equations in [17]:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_{11} &= f_{11}(x_{1,1}, x_{1,2}) \\ \dot{x}_{1,2} &= f_{1,2}(x_{1,1}, x_{1,2}, u_1^f) + d_1 \\ \dot{x}_{2,1} &= f_{2,1}(x_{2,1}, x_{2,2}) \\ \dot{x}_{2,2} &= f_{2,2}(x_{2,1}, x_{2,2}, u_2^f) + d_2\end{aligned}\tag{88}$$

where

$f_{1,1}(x_{1,1}, x_{1,2}) = 0.1x_{1,1}^2 + x_{1,2}; f_{1,2}(x_{1,1}, x_{1,2}, u_1^f) = x_{1,1}(0.1x_{1,2} - 0.2) + (2 + x_{1,1}^2)u_1(v_1) + \sin(u_1(v_1)) + x_{2,1}^2;$
 $f_{2,1}(x_{2,1}, x_{2,2}) = 0.1x_{2,1} + x_{2,2}; f_{2,2}(x_{2,1}, x_{2,2}, u_2^f) = -0.3x_{2,2} + 0.1(1 + \tanh(u_2(v_2))) + (1 + \sin^2(x_{2,1}))u_2(v_2)$
 $+ 0.5x_{1,1}x_{2,1}$ are unknown nonlinear functions. One can readily check that $g_{1,1} = \frac{\partial \dot{x}_{1,1}}{\partial x_{1,1}} = 1 > 0$, $g_{1,2} = \frac{\partial \dot{x}_{1,2}}{\partial u_1(v_1)} = 2 + x_{1,1}^2 + \cos(u_1(v_1)) > 0$, thus, $g_{1,1} \cdot g_{1,2} > 0$, which is consistent with the previously presented assumptions and definitions. The interconnection terms for both subsystems are given by $x_{2,1}^2$ and $0.5x_{1,1}x_{2,1}$, respectively. Furthermore, the structure of this mathematical system, in a pure-feedback configuration, is considerably more intricate, as it incorporates nonlinear non-affine components with respect to the control input and the system dynamics. The nonlinearities demonstrated in this case fully comply with the established theory. The external disturbances are defined as $d_1 = -\sin(t)$ and $d_2 = \sin(t)$, while the saturation bounds are set as $\bar{u}_{1M} = 2$ and $u_{2M} = 2$, along with the parameters of the anti-windup compensator as $k_{ie}, i=1:3 = 2.2, \bar{g} = 0.1, \eta_{i,0}, i=1:3 = 0.5$ and $\chi_{i,0}, i=1:2 = 0$.

The objective is to design and apply the proposed adaptive neural network (NN) controller such that the system output y accurately tracks the desired trajectory $y_{d,1} = 0.4 \sin(2t) - 0.7 \sin(t)$ and $y_{d,2} = 1 \sin(0.7t)$, While ensuring that all signals in the closed-loop system remain bounded and the system states stay within the desired constrained region, the transient and steady-state tracking error bounds are rigorously defined through a prescribed performance function $\mu_i(t) = (\mu_{i0} - \mu_{i\infty}) e^{-\kappa_i t} + \mu_{i\infty}$. For $i = 1, 2$, in which $\mu_{10} = \mu_{20} = 0.40, \mu_{1\infty} = \mu_{2\infty} = 0.05, \underline{\delta}_1 = \underline{\delta}_2 = 1, \bar{\delta}_1 = \bar{\delta}_2 = 1, \kappa_1 = \kappa_2 = 0.7$. To implement the control algorithm, the initial states are chosen as: $x_i(0) = [0.1, 0, 0.1, 0]^T, \hat{e}_i(0) = [0, 0, 0, 0]^T, \tau(0) = 0$. The design parameters used in this simulation are chosen as follows: $\Lambda_i = [0.8, 1000]^T, \gamma_i = 0.1, \epsilon_i = 0.02, \alpha_i = 10, \Gamma_{i0} = \Gamma_{ic} = \Gamma_{ia} = 0.01, \sigma_{i0} = 0.8, \sigma_{ic} = 10, \sigma_{ia} = 1.2, \sigma_{i2} = 0.08$ for $i = 1 : 2$. The feedback and observer gain vectors are determined based on the placement of desired poles using the pole placement (place) function and are given, for both subsystems, respectively, as follows: $k_{1c} = k_{2c} = [24.00, 26.00, 9.00]$, and $k_{1o} = k_{2o} = [0.007 \times 10^4, 0.15 \times 10^4, 1.125 \times 10^4]$. In addition, by selecting $Q_i = 100I_{3 \times 3}$ and by resolving the Lyapunov algebraic equation (26) we get the following positive definite symmetric matrix:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 81.0119 & -50.0000 & -77.1429 \\ -50.0000 & 77.1429 & -50.0000 \\ -77.1429 & -50.0000 & 355.7143 \end{bmatrix}$$

In this simulation study one NNs given by (12) is used to approach the unknown nonlinear dynamics for each subsystem. Each NN has $Z_{i0} = [X, k_i^T \hat{z}_i, \dot{v}_i(t), u_i(v_i(t))]^T$, $Z_{ic} = [X, \varphi_i, \vartheta_i, u_i(v_i(t))]^T$ and $Z_{ia} = [X, \varphi_i, u_i(v_i(t))]^T$, with hyperbolic tangent activation function and the initial NN weights $W_{i0}(0), W_{ic}(0), W_{ia}(0)$ are randomly selected in $[0 \ 1]$.

To illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed FTC method in Theorem 1, four types of actuator faults are considered: bias, drift, loss of accuracy, and loss of effectiveness. In comparison, the work in [16] addresses only three types of actuator faults.

The time-varying actuator faults considered for this example are chosen for both subsystems, as shown in the following Table 2:

Table 2: Time-varying Actuator faults

Type	Sub-system 1	Sub-system 2
Bias	0.1	0.1
Drift	0.01t	0.01t
Loss of accuracy	0.01square(t)	0.8 square (t)
Loss of effectiveness	70%	80%

From the simulation results, the system responses, tracking errors within prescribed bounds, observation errors, and control inputs are illustrated in Figs.1 - 5, respectively. As shown in Fig.1 and Fig.2, the system in 88 achieves satisfactory tracking performance in both the transient and steady-state phases, without violating the predesigned time-varying output constraints, even in the presence of actuator faults, unknown control directions, external disturbances, and approximation errors. Precise tracking of the desired trajectories for both subsystems is observed. Furthermore, Fig. 3 demonstrates the convergence of the observation errors to a small neighborhood around the origin, confirming the effectiveness of the implemented observer. On the other hand, Figs. 4 and 5 depict the control inputs, starting from the virtual control signals ω_i generated by the transformation controller governing the evolution of the intermediate variable v_i through $\dot{v} = \omega_i$ to the actual actuator inputs applied to the system. The control strategy explicitly accounts for actuator saturation limits as well as multiple types of actuator faults, including bias, drift, loss of accuracy, and loss of effectiveness. By integrating a smooth, hyperbolic tangent based saturation function into the auxiliary control law, the actual control inputs are consistently maintained within their allowable bounds, even under fault conditions.

Figure 1: The trajectory tracking for each subsystem in Example 1

Figure 2: The responses of the tracking errors and their upper and lower bounds in Example 1

Figure 3: Estimation errors of new states variables in Example 1

Figure 4: Control inputs in Example 1

Figure 5: Virtual control signals for each subsystem in Example 1

Example 2

The attitude dynamical model of a quadrotor helicopter is represented by Euler angles (φ, θ, ψ) under the conditions $(-\pi/2 < \varphi < \pi/2)$ for roll, $(-\pi/2 < \theta < \pi/2)$ for pitch, $(-\pi < \psi < \pi)$ for yaw. Thus, the mathematical model is described by [37, 18]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{x}_{1,1} &= x_{1,2} \\
 \dot{x}_{1,2} &= a_1 x_{2,2} x_{3,2} - a_2 \Omega_r x_{2,2} - a_3 x_{1,2} + b_1 u_\varphi(v) \\
 &\quad + d_{\dot{\varphi}}(t) \\
 \dot{x}_{2,1} &= x_{2,2} \\
 \dot{x}_{2,2} &= a_4 x_{1,2} x_{3,2} - a_5 \Omega_r x_{1,2} - a_6 x_{2,2} + b_2 u_\theta(v) \\
 &\quad + d_{\dot{\theta}}(t) \\
 \dot{x}_{3,1} &= x_{3,2} \\
 \dot{x}_{3,2} &= a_7 x_{1,2} x_{2,2} - a_8 x_{3,2} + b_3 u_\psi(v) \\
 &\quad + d_{\dot{\psi}}(t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{89}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= \frac{I_y - I_z}{I_x}, \quad a_2 = \frac{I_r}{I_x}, \quad a_3 = \frac{k_\varphi}{I_x}, \quad a_4 = \frac{I_z - I_x}{I_y}, \quad a_5 = \frac{J_r}{I_y}, \\ a_6 &= \frac{k_\theta}{I_y}, \quad a_7 = \frac{I_x - I_y}{I_z}, \quad a_8 = \frac{k_\psi}{I_z}, \quad b_1 = \frac{d}{I_x}, \quad b_2 = \frac{d}{I_y}, \quad b_3 = \frac{1}{I_z}, \\ \Omega_r &= w_1 - w_2 + w_3 - w_4 \end{aligned}$$

The system control input are selected as

$$\begin{cases} u_\varphi = b(w_4^2 - w_2^2) \\ u_\theta = b(w_3^2 - w_1^2) \\ u_\psi = \kappa(w_1^2 - w_2^2 + w_3^2 - w_4^2) \end{cases} \quad (90)$$

where $x = (\varphi, \dot{\varphi}, \theta, \dot{\theta}, \psi, \dot{\psi})$ is the vector of the roll angular rate, roll-velocity rate, pitch angular rate, pitch-velocity rate, yaw angular rate and yaw-velocity rate, respectively; and $v = [v_1, v_2, v_3]^T$ is the control input vector; $u = [u_\varphi, u_\theta, u_\psi]^T$ denotes the plant input vector subject to saturation nonlinearity. The specific numerical values corresponding to these parameters are provided in the subsequent table [18] as shown in Table 3 :

Table 3: Quadrotor physical parameters.

Parameter	Value
d	25 cm
J_r	$2.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$
I_x, I_y	$3.82 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$
I_z	$7.13 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$
k_φ, k_θ	$5.56 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}/\text{rad}$
k_ψ	$6.35 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}/\text{rad}$
b	$2.98 \times 10^{-5} \text{ N} \cdot \text{s}^2/\text{rad}^2$
κ	$3.23 \times 10^{-7} \text{ N} \cdot \text{s}^2/\text{rad}^2$

The external disturbances are given as

$$(d_{\dot{\varphi}}(t), d_{\dot{\theta}}(t), d_{\dot{\psi}}(t))^T = \text{diag}(a_3, a_6, a_8) \dot{\eta}_{air} \quad (91)$$

with $\dot{\eta}_{air} = (\dot{\varphi}_{air}, \dot{\theta}_{air}, \dot{\psi}_{air})^T$ represents the wind disturbances defined by the rotation velocity of the air with respect to the earth-fixed inertial frame. In addition, these wind disturbances are modeled by square waves form having velocities $\pm(30, 45, 60)^T \text{ deg/s}$ with a frequency of 0.1 Hz . Hence, the simulation objective is to apply the proposed adaptive NNs controller such that the system output $y_1 = [\varphi, \theta, \psi]^T$ tracks the desired trajectory $y_d = [\varphi_d, \theta_d, \psi_d]^T$. The desired trajectories are selected as sinusoidal signals having the following equation: $y_d = [\sin(t), \sin(t), \sin(t)]^T$, While ensuring that all signals in the closed-loop system remain bounded and the system states stay within the desired constrained region, the transient and steady-state tracking error bounds are rigorously defined through a prescribed performance function $\mu_i(t) = (\mu_{i0} - \mu_{i\infty}) e^{-\kappa_i t} + \mu_{i\infty}$. For $i = 1, 3$, in which $\mu_{10} = 0.65, \mu_{1\infty} = 0.09, \mu_{20} = 0.65, \mu_{2\infty} = 0.09, \mu_{30} = 0.65, \mu_{3\infty} = 0.09, \underline{\delta}_1 = 1, \bar{\delta}_1 = 1, \underline{\delta}_2 = 1, \bar{\delta}_2 = 1, \underline{\delta}_3 = 1, \bar{\delta}_3 = 1, \kappa_1 = \kappa_2 = \kappa_3 = 0.9$. To implement the control algorithm, the initial states are chosen as: $x_i(0) = [pi/20, 0, pi/20, 0, pi/20, 0]^T, \hat{e}_i(0) = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]^T, \tau(0) = 0$. The design parameters used in this simulation are chosen as follows: $\Lambda_i = [1.2, 0.5]^T, \gamma_i = 0.1, \epsilon_i = 0.01, \alpha_i = 4, \Gamma_{i0} = 60, \Gamma_{ic} = 0.1, \Gamma_{ia} = 50, \sigma_{i0} = 5.06, \sigma_{ic} = 40, \sigma_{ia} = 1.2, \sigma_{i2} = 20.1$ for $i = 1 : 3$. The quadrotor dynamics are simulated with input actuator saturation limit $u_{iM}, i=1:3 = 0.2 [N.M]$ along with the parameters of the anti-windup compensator as $k_{ie}, i=1:3 = 2.2, \bar{g} = 0.1, \eta_{i,0}, i=1:3 = 0.5$ and $\chi_{i,0}, i=1:3 = 0$.

The observer and controller gain for the proposed controller are selected as

$$k_{io} = \begin{bmatrix} 512.7 & 144.2 & 1048 & 242.9 & 0 & 0 \\ 595.8 & 162.7 & 1681.6 & 394.4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 825.9 & 61.1 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$k_{ic} = \begin{bmatrix} 10.60 & 21.90 & 3.10 & 10.40 & 0 & 0 \\ 3.10 & 10.40 & 9.80 & 19.30 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 96.0 & 1247.8 \end{bmatrix}$$

In addition, by selecting $Q_i = 10I_{6 \times 6}$, and by resolving the Lyapunov algebraic equation (26) we get the following positive definite symmetric matrix:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.561 & 0.307 & -0.196 & -0.166 & 0.000 & -0.0002 \\ 0.307 & 12.963 & -0.166 & 1.397 & 0.000 & -0.0006 \\ -0.196 & -0.166 & 0.610 & 0.349 & -0.000 & 0.0002 \\ -0.166 & 1.397 & 0.349 & 12.605 & -0.000 & 0.0007 \\ 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.000 & -0.000 & 0.052 & 0.004 \\ -0.0002 & -0.0006 & 0.0002 & 0.0007 & 0.004 & 65.424 \end{bmatrix}$$

In this simulation study one NNs given by (12) is used to approach the unknown nonlinear dynamics for each subsystem. Each NNs has $Z_{i0} = [X, k_i^T \hat{z}_i, \dot{v}_i(t), u_i(v_i(t))]^T$, $Z_{ic} = [X, \varphi_i, \vartheta_i, u_i(v_i(t))]^T$ and $Z_{ia} = [X, \varphi_i, u_i(v_i(t))]^T$, with hyperbolic tangent activation function and the initial NN weights $W_{io}(0), W_{ic}(0), W_{ia}(0)$ are randomly selected in $[0 \ 1]$.

In order to verify the effectiveness and performance of the proposed controller, we apply three actuator fault terms $f_{a\varphi}$, $f_{a\theta}$ and $f_{a\psi}$ as the control inputs u_φ , u_θ and u_ψ at the same instants $T_{fi} \geq 2s$. For this simulation, four different kinds of actuator problems are taken into account, as shown in Table 4 below.

Table 4: UAV actuator faults.

Type	Roll	Pitch	Yaw
Bias	0.02.(rad)	0.025.(rad)	0.062.(rad)
Drift	0.06t.(rad)	0.06t.(rad)	0.012t.(rad)
Loss of accuracy	0.008square(t).(rad)	0.008square(t).(rad)	0.008square(t).(rad)
Loss of effectiveness	80%	80%	90%

The simulation results are illustrated in Figs 6 – 9. from fig.6 the system output (φ, θ, ψ) velocities follow the desired trajectories $(\varphi_d, \theta_d, \psi_d)$ very well. From fig.7 the tracking error, roll angle, pitch angle and yaw angle convergence into a small neighborhood of zero and evolves within output constraints for all $t \geq 0$. It is clear that the designed observer is able to provide very good estimation of the unavailable new defined states as shown in fig.8. Meanwhile, fig.9 show the control inputs of the quadrotor helicopter. Although, the designed auxiliary control inputs may exceed the saturation bound, the actual control inputs of the quadrotor helicopter are always in the saturation range using a hyperbolic tangent function.

From the simulation results, we can observe that the proposed methods are able to control a quadrotor helicopter system with effective performance in the presence of unknown input nonlinearities and preserving smooth trajectories for all the states and the control input signals.

The simulation results, presented in Figs. 6–9, validate the effectiveness of the proposed control strategy. Figs. 6 and 7 show that the system in (66) achieves excellent tracking performance in both transient and steady-state phases, without violating the predesigned time-varying output constraints, even in the presence of actuator faults, unknown control directions, external disturbances, and approximation errors. Specifically, Fig. 6 illustrates that the system output velocities (φ, θ, ψ) closely follow the desired trajectories $(\varphi_d, \theta_d, \psi_d)$, achieving high tracking accuracy for all three angles and their corresponding velocities. Meanwhile, Fig. 7 shows that the tracking errors for the roll, pitch, and yaw angles converge rapidly to a small neighborhood around zero while consistently satisfying the prescribed output constraints for all $t \geq 0$. The proposed observer provides accurate estimation of the newly defined as depicted in Fig. 8. Fig. 9 presents the control inputs of the quadrotor helicopter

under actuator faults. Despite fault effects, the actual control inputs remain within the allowable saturation limits due to the use of a smooth hyperbolic tangent function, although the auxiliary control signals may temporarily exceed these limits. Finally, Fig. 10 shows the trajectories of ω_i , confirming their boundedness. Overall, these results demonstrate that the proposed fault-tolerant control scheme successfully compensates for actuator faults, ensuring precise trajectory tracking, smooth and bounded control actions, and robust performance in the presence of unknown input nonlinearities.

Figure 6: The trajectory tracking for each subsystem in Example 2

Figure 7: The responses of the tracking errors and their upper and lower bounds in Example 2

Figure 8: Estimation errors of new states variables in Example 2

Figure 9: Control input signals u_ϕ , u_θ and u_ψ with the saturation input signals v_ϕ , v_θ and v_ψ in Example 2

Figure 10: Virtual control signals $\omega_\phi, \omega_\theta$ and ω_ψ in Example 2

5. Conclusion

In this paper, an adaptive neural tracking control design with output constraint has been developed for the MIMO pure-feedback nonlinear system with input nonlinearity, faulty actuators, unknown uncertainties, and external disturbances. The advantage of the proposed design is that it can not only handle the problem of constraints, but also the design structure is universal for different systems with only a few adjustable parameters. Lyapunov analysis has proven the stability of the closed-loop system. Both a mathematical model and a quadrotor helicopter system illustrate the performance of the proposed control scheme.

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